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Abstract

The study aims to identify the substantial and pervasive changes that are taking place in social media, which facilitate the development of online community networks. It is no doubt that the Internet and the community media are powerful instruments for mobilization of people by which it forces and shapes human conduct. All over the world, billions of us use community media every day, and that number just changing the way we communicate – it’s developing the way we do business, the way we are supervise, and the way we live in a community. It not only helps the users in a variety of ways but also it poses threats to them in other ways. Traditionally, consumers use cyberspace to read, watch, and to buy products and services. Social media help the society in different ways, in the form of social media platforms like blogs (Tumblr, Word Press), community networks (Facebook, Instagram), social news sites (Digg, Reddit) and wikis (Wikipedia). Since it has been responsible for relevant changes that catch place in the community, in these, websites are here for human interaction.

Keywords: Social Media, Social Networking, E-Commerce.

Introduction

This paper discusses the importance of social media and social networking among men and women of three different age groups, ie Young, middle and, old age and the preferences towards community networking. It has been analyzed that social networks among men and women differ in many ways, particularly in connection to growth stage. The last ten years have seen a rise in social media impact, not only in terms of exchanging of data, but also in terms of business, travel, tourism, relationships, food, etc. community media has greatly affected the way people donate their free time. Disappeared those days when community frequented parks or libraries during their free time. These collective networks open up the possibilities of discovering and learning new information, sharing ideas and interacting with others. Social media such as LinkedIn allows people to create professional networks that help them search for jobs or get tips on how to enhance their careers.

Social Media helps Marketers in attracting new clients and promoting products and services. The new generation has grabbed many things from community hobnob because it helps in developing their communication skills and also teaches them to work within a group. Superiors of political notables turn on to social media to connect with their followers and make new ones. And these sites also are used to perform another day to day activities such as paying different bills and of transacting money and to avail other multiple benefits.

Landing of the community networking floor helped to enhance the relation between the people and business. Globe has become a smaller place thanks to face book, whatsapp and, twitter, where people can meet their friends and colleagues, both old and new. They can post their logics, chat, or even play games. In simple, it is a digital globe of entertainment and information for the users, and it is difficult to imagine life without the presence of social media sites as they provide multiple benefits to the users, besides of posting pictures or videos. Many things glimpse and atmosphere easier to do with community media. It is considered as a powerful platform for social activism where people can collaborate to highlight the social causes affecting society through social media.

Objectives

1. To explore the impact of social media on people’s relationships, especially the family, gender, intimate relationships, and friendships.
2. To study how social media has been used in learning, marketing, and other fields.
3. To find out the confident and adverse impacts of social media among different age groups.
4. To interpret the different usage patterns of social media and networking sites by the offender.

Difference between Social Media and Social Networking

It is very crucial to accept that community media and social networking are not one and the same but they are both of critical importance. Social media and social networking have been instrumental in many events around the world. Many association thinks that social media and social networking are the same and accordingly can be used interchangeably. The difference between social media and social networking is that social media helps people to make the connection and social networking enhances that connection.

Some of the most popular community media websites are Facebook, WhatsApp, Instagram, Twitter, Pinterest, LinkedIn, Google+, YouTube, etc. These community media websites have more than 100,000,000 registered users. A social networkingservice (also social networkingsite, SNS or socialmedia) is an online platform that is used by people to build social networks or social relations with the different associations who share similar personal or career interests, activities, backgrounds or real-life connections.

Positive and Negative Impacts of Social Media in the Nation

Surfing on Social Media websites can make you feel connected to a community. But it has some advantages and disadvantages also.

Positive Impact: Older adults are at increased risk of experiencing loneliness and depression, and the benefit of social media for the elderly population is the possibility to keep in touch with friends and family through social networking sites. More importantly, they can share their problems with others, from the comfort and privacy of their own homes. Social media is helping us better respond to disasters; many examples have shown how social media and digital communications more broadly are helping respond to disasters. Social media is helping us appliance some of the world’s biggest challenges, from human rights violations to climate change. Social media is changing how we govern and are governed Whereas politicians and government officials once had

to travel to interact with citizens, now online town halls strengthen the relations between them while providing a platform for direct input on government initiatives. For the youngsters, it helps to develop awareness about the society and the world. It helps them to groom their social skills and to expand their social circle, and the increasing Internet diffusion and availability of more remittance options boosted the e-commerce industry at a higher rate.

Negative Impacts: The prime effect is dependence on checking Facebook, WhatsApp, Twitter, and other community media updates. This dependence could adversely affect other valued activities like concentrating on studies, taking active part in sports, real-life contact and ignoring ground realities and in all sectors of life. Plenty of investigation seems to indicate that in young adults, Facebook use leads to a downturn in subjective well-being, especially children are very sensitive to cyber-bullying. Over community announcement, it's easier for bullies to intimidate their victims anonymously, and this will tend to deep mental scars at the people who are getting harassed. The primary reason for suicidal thinking is the invisibility that the annoyer supports online and that is all with the help of social media websites. Social media motive not only problems for individual people, but it's also a problem for many businesses nowadays. Today there is a lot of violence in video games and movies, and the amount of sex in media can make a youth scary and confused and unable to distinguish between reality and fantasy, which lead to violence and irresponsible sexual behavior and unwanted pregnancies. Playing outside becomes a rarity as they spent much time in front of the TV or computer leads to obesity.

The Usage Pattern of Social Media Users

Social media is a central presence of marketing today. According to Hanna et al. (2011), social media is not an optional part of a marketing strategy but a mandatory component for most companies today. Community media usage is immediately spreading Facebook, the global social network has over 1.19 billion users with an annual growth rate of eighteen percent (Aichner & Jacob 2015). Again the increase in community media usage, many associations today does not fully understand the social media user. Through the last ten years, millions of internet users around the world have visited a large number of social networking and social media sites (Kim, Jeong, & Lee, 2010). Moradabadi, Gharehshiran, and Amrai (2012) mentioned that motives for using Facebook are for knowledge sharing, freedom of contact, free flow, control of information, sense of equality, and requirement for information and entertainment. A 2015 study shows that certain crowd uses social networking sites for their purchase decision making. While some people aged 55 and over commit to word of mouth. Research has provided us with varied outcomes as to whether or not a person's involvement in social networking can affect their feelings of loneliness. An expanding volume of associations are peer to the Internet and social media to fulfill cognitive, affective, personal integrative, civil integrative, and tension free needs. With information technology automation as a supplement to fulfill needs, it is, in turn, affecting life, including relationships. School, church, entertainment, and family. Based on the internet shopping study by Ernst and Young (1999), the two reasons for consumers to shop online are increased convenience and savings. Social media is switch banking contacts in very symbolic ways, from correcting customer service to allowing users to send money to others via online platforms. New commercial technology associations are using social media to help people simply open a bank account. Social media can even crush your ability to get a loan. A few years ago, Social Media wasn't that big yet, but nowadays, people can use it for almost anything in their daily life. Why would anyone buy CDs when we have YouTube? Why would a nation buy newspapers when we have Facebook and Twitter? When you just wake up and open your eyes, you don't have to go out from bed to see what's going on in the rest of the world. They introduce substantial, and pervasive changes to communication between businesses, organizations, communities and individuals and everything by their door step.

Findings

A short sample method was adopted for the current subject. A Public opinion pool was used as an appliance for meeting testimony. It was formulated keeping in mind the intension of the study. A total of 100 questionnaires were distributed among three diverse life circles. But accepted acknowledgments from only 50 defendants of both men and women. The preferences toward social media and social networking on different aspects are shown using a bar diagram. The questionnaire consists of demographic variable as age, sex, education, occupation, and the preferences towards different social networking sites and also the purpose of usage. This study gathered the opinions and attitudes of 100 respondents,

The Diagram shows the defendants preferences towards various networking sites.

Perceived Usefulness is one key predicting factor. Young and the older adults feel that social networking websites are useful, they have more interest in using them in the future and use them for more hours during the week. Usefulness is measured in terms of how much an individual thinks the website can be used to meet certain goals. Perceived Ease of Use is another factor. Just like usefulness, ease of use also correlates with interest in using social networking websites and hours of use. Ease of use relates both to how easy it is to get a website to do what you want it to do and also to how easy it is to use social networking websites. Collective burden one more time shows a display in patterns of use. In this study, no differences were found between men and women. Both expressed modifying community networking websites in relatively balanced percentages. Correspondingly, in that matter, there was no relation base among a formation of education and interest in handling implication: the older the participant, the less interest in social networking websites. The freedom to manage social affair is specifically for the elderly. Whats app, Facebook, etc. show 100% of responses where people get together of common interests, passions, and causes and continue to strengthen their relationships as they get to know each other through interaction over time. 75% preferences given to online payment options and equal importance is given to teaching and for e-commerce business of 65%. In this consideration, members who observe that social networking website use was associated with negative consequences were less likely to report interest in using the websites in the future. Social media can generate it challenging for us to distinguish between relationships from the real world and relationships formed through social media. Believe of common Networking Websites is also to consider. May be those end users who previously use social networking websites are more inclined to trust them.

Conclusion

It is contemporary to attack the communication media for everything that ails society today. But is media so evil? It is not an addiction for kids and teens but for very mature and influential personalities too. If there is consciousness around the danger of social media in our community, it will not lead to anything bad but there is always lack of public awareness and as specified above that the chart of internet users is getting higher and higher while we are still far behind in the field of education thus public awareness is very difficult in societies with lack of education. Due to our social media contacts, there will be a higher chance that greater meaningful relationships will weaken. The fact is that there are advantages and disadvantages of social media. Many news reports these days are periodically featured information about the dangers of distribution of information online. Though all social networking websites navigate and use. In this application, hope in collective networking websites was also associated with a higher interest in using the internet sites. May be those end users who previously use social networking websites are more inclined to trust them. But not all of them have considered social media so positively. Advice on collective Networking Websites and Older Adults. Including appropriate confidentiality scenery set up and some common sense about what information is shared, there is no risk in using social networking websites. Using these guidelines, you should increase your chances of success. Collective networking website use among older adults is growing, so position yourself to take advantage! In order to get older people to use collective networks family members, care-givers, community facilitators and trainers should step in and assist. At the same time, design and enjoyer neighborliness need to be addressed by social network developers.

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